

On Support Vector Machines under a multiple-cost scenario

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Abstract Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a powerful tool in binary classification, known to attain excellent misclassification rates. On the other hand, many realworld classification problems, such as those found in medical diagnosis, churn or fraud prediction, involve misclassification costs which may be different in the different classes. However, it may be hard for the user to provide precise values for such misclassification costs, whereas it may be much easier to identify acceptable misclassification rates values. In this paper we propose a novel SVM model in which misclassification costs are considered by incorporating performance constraints in the problem formulation. Specifically, our aim is to seek the hyperplane with maximal margin yielding misclassification rates below given threshold values. Such maximal margin hyperplane is obtained by solving a quadratic convex problem with linear constraints and integer variables. The reported numerical experience shows that our model gives the user control on the misclassification rates in one class (possibly at

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the expense of an increase in misclassification rates for the other class) and is feasible in terms of running times.

Keywords Constrained Classification · Misclassification costs · Mixed Integer Quadratic Programming · Sensitivity/Specificity trade-off · Support Vector Machines

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1 Introduction

In supervised classification we are given a set Ω of individuals belonging to two or more different classes, and the final aim is to classify new objects whose class is unknown. Each object $i \in \Omega$ can be represented by a pair (x_i, y_i) , where $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the attribute vector and $y_i \in \mathcal{C}$ is the class membership of object i .

A state-of-the-art method in supervised classification is the support vector machine (SVM), see Vapnik (1995, 1998); Cristianini and Shawe-Taylor (2000); Carrizosa and Romero Morales (2013). In its basic version, SVM addresses two-class problems, i.e., \mathcal{C} has two elements, say, $\mathcal{C} = \{-1, +1\}$. The SVM aims at separating both classes by means of a linear classifier, $\omega^\top x + \beta = 0$, where ω is the so called *score vector*. We will assume throughout this paper that $\mathcal{C} = \{-1, +1\}$ and refer the reader to e.g. Allwein et al. (2001) for the reduction of multiclass problems to this case.

The linear SVM classifier is obtained by solving the following convex quadratic programming (QP) formulation with linear constraints:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\omega, \beta, \xi} \quad & \omega^\top \omega + C_+ \sum_{i \in I: y_i = +1} \xi_i + C_- \sum_{i \in I: y_i = -1} \xi_i \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & y_i(\omega^\top x_i + \beta) \geq 1 - \xi_i, & i \in I \\ & \xi_i \geq 0 & i \in I, \end{aligned} \tag{SVM}(C_+, C_-)$$

where I represents the set of training data, $\xi_i \geq 0$ are artificial variables which allow data points to be misclassified, and $C_+, C_- > 0$ are *regularization parameters* to be tuned that control the trade-off between margin minimization and misclassification errors. The case $C_+ = C_-$ is frequently considered in the literature, but the use of different regularization parameters for the different classes may allow for a better control of misclassification costs or unbalancedness. See e.g. Lin et al. (2002).

Given an object i , it is classified in the positive or the negative class according to the sign of the so-called score function, $\text{sign}(\omega^\top x_i + \beta)$, while for the case $\omega^\top x_i + \beta = 0$, the object is classified randomly.

A mapping into a high-dimensional feature space may be considered (Cortes and Vapnik (1995)), which allows us to transform this linear classification

technique in a non-linear one using Mercer Theorem, Mercer (1909) and the so-called kernel trick, e.g. Cristianini and Shawe-Taylor (2000). In this way we can address problems with a very large number of features, such as those encountered in personalized medicine (Sánchez et al. 2016).

Hence, the general formulation of SVM is

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{\lambda} \quad & -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{jk} \lambda_j \lambda_k y_j y_k K(x_j, x_k) + \sum_l \lambda_l \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \sum_i \lambda_i y_i = 0 \\ & 0 \leq \lambda_i \leq C_+, \quad i \in I : y_i = +1 \\ & 0 \leq \lambda_i \leq C_-, \quad i \in I : y_i = -1, \end{aligned}$$

where $K : \mathbb{R}^m \times \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a kernel function and λ are the usual variables of the dual formulation of the SVM.

As mentioned, the goal in supervised classification is to classify objects in the correct class. However, ignoring imbalance (either in the classes size, either in the misclassification cost structure) may have dramatic consequences in the classification task, see Carrizosa et al. (2008); He and Ma (2013); Prati et al. (2015); Maldonado et al. (2017). For instance, for clinical databases, there are usually more observations of healthy populations than of the disease cases, and therefore smaller classification errors may be obtained for the first case. For example, for the well known *Breast Cancer Wisconsin (Diagnostic) Data Set* from the UCI repository (Lichman 2013), the number of sick cases (212) is smaller than the size of control cases (357). If a standard SVM is used for classifying the dataset, then the estimated rates (average values according to a 10-fold cross-validation approach), are depicted in Table 1. Even though both

	Mean	Std
% benign instances well classified	99%	1.7
% malignant instances well classified	94.8%	4.9

Table 1 Performance of standard SVM with Radial Function Basis kernel in `wisconsin`. Average values and standard deviations computed from 10 realizations.

rates are high, it might be of interest to increase the accuracy of predicting cancer, perhaps at the expense of deteriorating the classification rates in the other class. This problem will be addressed in this paper.

In order to cope with imbalancedness, either in class size or structure of misclassification costs, different methods have been suggested, see Bradford et al. (1998); Freitas et al. (2007); Carrizosa et al. (2008); Datta and Das (2015). Those methods are based on adding parameters or adapting the classifier construction, among others. For example, in Carrizosa et al. (2008) a biobjective problem of simultaneous minimization of misclassification rate, via the maximization of the margin, and measurement costs, is formulated.

In this paper a new formulation of the SVM is presented, in such a way that the focus is not only on the minimization of the overall misclassification rate but also on the performance of the classifier in the two classes (either jointly or separately). In order to do that, novel constraints are added to the SVM formulation. The keystone of the new model is its ability to achieve a deeper control over misclassification in contrast to previously existing models. The proposed methodology will be called Constrained Support Vector Machine (CSVM) and the resulting classification technique will be referred as CSVM classifier.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, the CSVM is formulated as an optimization problem, and details concerning its feasibility are given. Section 3 aims to illustrate the performance of the new classifier. A description in depth about the experiments' design, real datasets to be tested as well as the obtained results will be given. The paper ends with some concluding remarks and possible extensions in Section 4.

2 Constrained Support Vector Machines

In this section the Constrained Support Vector Machine (CSVM) model is formulated as a Mixed Integer Nonlinear Programming (MINLP) problem (Bonami et al. 2008; Burer and Letchford 2012), specifically in terms of a Mixed Integer Quadratic Programming (MIQP) problem.

This section is structured as follows. In Section 2.1 some theoretical foundations that motivate the novel constraints are given. Then, in Section 2.2 the formulation of the CSVM is presented. We will depart from the linear kernel case to later extend it to the general kernel case via the kernel trick. Finally, in Section 2.3, some issues about the CSVM formulation, as its feasibility, shall be discussed.

2.1 Theoretical Motivation

As commented before, the aim of this work is to build a classifier so that the user may have control over the performance over the two classes. Specifically, given a set $\Omega = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_i$ of data (a random sample of a vector (X, Y) with unknown distribution), the target is to obtain a classifier such that $p \geq p_0$, where p is the value of a performance measurement and p_0 is a threshold chosen by the user. The performance measure p is chosen by the user at her convenience and may be selected among the following rates: true positive rate (TPR) or sensitivity, true negative rate (TNR) or specificity and accuracy (ACC), which are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{TPR} : p &= P(\omega^\top X + \beta > 0 | Y = +1) \\ \text{TNR} : p &= P(\omega^\top X + \beta < 0 | Y = -1) \\ \text{ACC} : p &= P(Y(\omega^\top X + \beta) > 0), \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

see for example, Bewick et al. (2004).

In this paper, for the sake of clarity, the positive class shall be identified with the class of interest to be controlled. For instance, in cancer screening studies, cancer is labelled as positive class whereas absence of cancer is labelled as negative. Also, in credit-scoring applications the positive class will be the defaulting clients. More examples will be discussed in Section 3.

If the random variable Z , defined as

$$Z = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if an observation is well classified,} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

is considered, then, the values of p as in (1) corresponding to the probability of correct classification can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{TPR} : p &= E[Z|Y = +1] \\ \text{TNR} : p &= E[Z|Y = -1] \\ \text{ACC} : p &= E[Z] \end{aligned}$$

and estimated from an independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) sample $\{Z_i\}_{i \in S}$, by

$$\begin{aligned} \text{TPR} : \hat{p} = \bar{Z}_+ &= \frac{\sum_{i \in S_+} Z_i}{|S_+|} \\ \text{TNR} : \hat{p} = \bar{Z}_- &= \frac{\sum_{i \in S_-} Z_i}{|S_-|} \\ \text{ACC} : \hat{p} = \bar{Z} &= \frac{\sum_{i \in S} Z_i}{|S|}, \end{aligned}$$

where S_+ and S_- denote, respectively, the subsets $\{i \in S : y_i = +1\}$ and $\{i \in S : y_i = -1\}$.

From a hypothesis testing viewpoint, our aim is to build a classifier such that, for a given sample, one can reject the null hypothesis in

$$\begin{cases} H_0 : p \leq p_0 \\ H_1 : p > p_0. \end{cases}$$

Under the classic decision rule, H_0 is rejected if $\hat{p} \geq p_0^*$ assuming that $\alpha = P(\text{type I error})$. From Hoeffding Inequality (Hoeffding 1963),

$$P(\hat{p} \geq p + c) \leq \exp(-2nc^2). \quad (2)$$

As $\alpha = P(\text{type I error}) = P(\hat{p} \geq p_0^* | p = p_0)$, substituting p by p_0 in (2) yields

$$P(\hat{p} < p_0 + c) \geq 1 - \exp(-2nc^2) = 1 - \alpha, \quad (3)$$

where $p_0 + c = p_0^*$. Therefore, we can take

$$p_0^* = p_0 + \sqrt{\frac{\log \alpha}{-2n}}. \quad (4)$$

Note that n equals $|S_+|$, $|S_-|$ or $|S|$, respectively, when considering the TPR, the TNR or the accuracy.

Here, the selection of the Hoeffding Inequality is motivated by its distribution-free character, but other options as the Binomial-Normal approximation could have been chosen instead.

2.2 CSVM formulation

In this section, the CSVM formulation is presented. As it will be seen, the formulation includes novel performance constraints, which make the optimization problem a MIQP problem in terms of some integer variables.

We assume to be given a dataset with known labels. From such set we identify the training set I , used to build the classifier, and the anchor set J , used to impose a lower bound on the classifier performance. These sets will be considered disjoint.

With the purpose of building the CSVM, the performance constraints will be formulated in terms of binary variables $\{z_j\}_{j \in J}$, which are realizations of the variable Z in Section 2.1 and defined as:

$$z_j = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if instance } j \text{ is counted as well classified} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

In order to formulate the CSVM, novel constraints are added to the standard soft-margin SVM formulation as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\omega, \beta, \xi, z} \quad & \omega^\top \omega + C_+ \sum_{i \in I: y_i = +1} \xi_i + C_- \sum_{i \in I: y_i = -1} \xi_i \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & y_i(\omega^\top x_i + \beta) \geq 1 - \xi_i, \quad i \in I \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\xi_i \geq 0 \quad i \in I \quad (6)$$

$$y_j(\omega^\top x_j + \beta) \geq 1 - M_1(1 - z_j), \quad j \in J \quad (7)$$

$$z_j \in \{0, 1\} \quad j \in J \quad (8)$$

$$\hat{p}_\ell \geq p_{0\ell}^* \quad \ell \in L. \quad (9)$$

(CSVM₀)

In the previous optimization problem, (5) and (6) are the usual constraints in the SVM formulation. Constraints (7) ensure that observations $j \in J$ with $z_j = 1$ will be correctly classified, without imposing any restriction when $z_j = 0$, provided that M_1 is big enough. A collection of requirements on the performance of the classifier over J can be specified by means of (9). Also, L is the set of indexes of the constraints that has the form of (9). These constraints can be modeled via the binary variables z_j , for instance:

$$\text{TPR} : \sum_{j \in J_+} z_j \geq p_0^* |J_+|$$

$$\text{TNR} : \sum_{j \in J_-} z_j \geq p_0^* |J_-|$$

$$\text{ACC} : \sum_{j \in J} z_j \geq p_0^* |J|,$$

where J_+ and J_- denote, respectively, the subsets $\{i \in J : y_i = +1\}$ and $\{i \in J : y_i = -1\}$.

As before, by considering the (partial) dual problem of (CSVM₀) and the *kernel trick*, the general formulation of the CSVM is obtained as follows (the intermediate steps can be found in Appendix A):

$$\begin{aligned}
& \min_{\lambda, \mu, \beta, \xi, z} && \sum_{s, s' \in I} \lambda_s y_s \lambda_{s'} y_{s'} K(x_s, x_{s'}) + \sum_{t, t' \in J} \mu_t y_t \mu_{t'} y_{t'} K(x_t, x_{t'}) \\
& && + 2 \sum_{s \in I, t \in J} \lambda_s y_s \mu_t y_t K(x_s, x_t) + C_+ \sum_{i \in I: y_i = +1} \xi_i + C_- \sum_{i \in I: y_i = -1} \xi_i \\
& \text{s.t.} && z_j \in \{0, 1\} && j \in J \\
& && \hat{p}_\ell \geq p_{0\ell}^* && \ell \in L \\
& && y_i \left(\sum_{s \in I} \lambda_s y_s K(x_s, x_i) + \sum_{t \in J} \mu_t y_t K(x_t, x_i) + \beta \right) \geq 1 - \xi_i && i \in I \\
& && y_j \left(\sum_{s \in I} \lambda_s y_s K(x_s, x_j) + \sum_{t \in J} \mu_t y_t K(x_t, x_j) + \beta \right) \geq 1 - M_1(1 - z_j) && j \in J \quad (\text{CSVM}) \\
& && \xi_i \geq 0 && i \in I \\
& && \sum_{i \in I} \lambda_i y_i + \sum_{j \in J} \mu_j y_j = 0 \\
& && 0 \leq \lambda_i \leq C_+/2 && i \in I: y_i = +1 \\
& && 0 \leq \lambda_i \leq C_-/2 && i \in I: y_i = -1 \\
& && 0 \leq \mu_j \leq M_2 z_j && j \in J.
\end{aligned}$$

Here $K : \mathbb{R}^m \times \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is again a kernel function, M_1 and M_2 are big enough numbers, and (λ, μ) are the usual variables in the dual formulation of the SVM.

2.3 Solving the CSVM

In this section we give details about the complexity of our problem as formulated in (CSVM). The problem belongs to the class of MIQP problems, and thus it can be addressed by standard mixed integer quadratic optimization solvers. In particular, the solver Gurobi (Gurobi Optimization 2016) and its Python language interface (Van Rossum and Drake 2011) have been used in our numerical experiments. In contrast to the standard SVM formulation, which is a continuous quadratic problem, the CSVM is harder to solve due to the presence of binary variables. Hence, the optimal solution may not be found in a short period of time; however, as discussed in our numerical experience, good results are obtained when the problems are solved heuristically by imposing a short time limit to the solver.

Performance constraints (9) may define an infeasible problem since the values of the $p_{0\ell}^*$ may be unattainable in practice. Hence, the study of the feasibility of Problem (CSVM) is an important issue. As an example, consider data composed by two different classes, each one represented respectively by black

Fig. 1 Study of feasibility and unfeasibility of the CSVM.

1

and white dots in the top picture in Figure 1. If the optimization problem for the linear kernel SVM is solved, the resulting classifier is a hyperplane that aims at separating both classes and maximizes the margin. An approximate

representation of the data and the classifier is shown in the middle panel in Figure 1. If the aim is to correctly classify all the data corresponding to a given class, it is intuitively easy to see that this objective can be reached by moving the SVM hyperplane. In fact, it can be seen in the bottom picture in Figure 1 how hyperplanes 1 and 2 classify correctly all white points, and hyperplane 3 classifies all the black dots in the correct class. Among all those hyperplanes, the SVM selects the one which maximizes the margin. So, intuitively, it is evident that if just one constraint of performance is imposed in only one of the classes, the problem is always feasible. However, and using the data in Figure 1 again, as well as the linear kernel SVM, it is clear that it is impossible to classify correctly all the instances at the same time; thus, the problem is then infeasible. However, there exist results, as Theorem 5 in Burges (1998), that show that the class of Mercer kernels for which $K(x, x') \rightarrow 0$ as $\|x - x'\| \rightarrow \infty$, and for which $K(x, x)$ is $O(1)$, builds classifiers that get a total correct classification in all the classes in the training sample, without regard how arbitrarily the data have been chosen. Thus, if a kernel satisfies the previous conditions, then feasibility is guaranteed. In particular, Radial Function Basis (RBF) kernel meets these conditions. Therefore, to be on the safe side, if the performance thresholds imposed are not too low, they should refer only to one class misclassification rates (so that we can shift the variable β to make the problem feasible) or to use a kernel, such as the RBF, known to have large VC dimension (Burges 1998; Cristianini and Shawe-Taylor 2000), defined as the maximal training sample size for which perfect separation can always be enforced.

3 Computational results

This section illustrates the performance of the novel method, the CSVM, in comparison with benchmark approaches. To do that, an assortment of datasets with different properties concerning size and unbalanceness shall be analyzed. Section 3.1 describes the experiments to be carried out, while Section 3.2 details the choice of parameters. Section 3.3 is devoted to clarify different aspects of the cross-validation procedure for estimating the performance of the approach, and Section 3.4 presents the datasets to be analyzed. Finally, Section 3.5 contains the obtained results and a deep discussion about them.

3.1 Description of the experiments

The objective of this paper, as has been stated before, is to build a classifier whose performance can be controlled by means of some constraints, as in Problem (CSVM). As explained in Section 2.1, if we want a performance measurement p to be greater than a value p_0 with a specified confidence $100(1 - \alpha)\%$, we should use an estimator of p , \hat{p} , and impose it to be greater than $p_0^* = p_0 + \sqrt{\frac{\log \alpha}{-2n}}$, according to (4).

Experiments whose aim will be to increase the performance rate of interest in one class will be performed. However, as it will be shown, a damage may be produced in the other class. In particular, since the interest is to improve the classification in the positive class, the TPR will be the rate to be included in the novel constraints. Assume that an estimator of the TPR, TPR_0 is given. The aim will be to impose $\text{TPR} \geq \text{TPR}_0 + \delta_1$, where $\delta_1 = 0.025$, although other values can also be tested. Therefore, our experiments will consist of:

$$\text{Impose } \text{TPR} \geq \min \{1, \text{TPR}_0 + 0.025\} = p_0,$$

which implies that, for $\alpha = 0.05$, the performance constraints in the optimization problem defining the novel CSVM are:

$$\widehat{\text{TPR}} \geq \min \left\{ 1, \text{TPR}_0 + \sqrt{\frac{\log 0.05}{-2n}} + 0.025 \right\} = p_0^*.$$

The novel CSVM will be compared with benchmark approaches. The first method to be compared with is the classic SVM where two different values of C (C_+ and C_-) are used for each class. This approach shall be noted as $\text{SVM}(C_+, C_-)$ (see Section 1). The second benchmark method consists of moving the original hyperplane resulting from performing the standard SVM until the value p_0^* obtained by Hoeffding Inequality is achieved. This approach will be called from now on *Sliding β strategy*.

3.2 Parameters Setting

One of the most popular kernels $K(x, x')$ in literature is the well-known RBF kernel (Cristianini and Shawe-Taylor 2000; Hastie et al. 2001; Hsu et al. 2003; Smola and Schölkopf 2004; Horn et al. 2016), given by

$$K(x, x') = \exp(-\gamma \|x - x'\|^2),$$

where $\gamma > 0$ is a parameter to be tuned. This will be the kernel chosen for implementing the CSVM, although the method is valid for an arbitrary kernel.

The time limit for the solver was set equal to 300 seconds. In addition, the M_1 and M_2 values in Problem (CSVM) were set both equal to 100. The choice of these values is motivated as follows. First, for the sake of computational tractability, the time limit should not be too high, but high enough so that the optimizer is able to solve the problem or at least to provide good feasible solutions. In our experiments, the choice of a time limit equal to 300s gave a good balance between the computational cost and the quality of the solutions. In the case of the values of M_1 and M_2 , if small values are chosen, there may be many discarded hyperplanes, including the optimal one. However, if M_1 and M_2 are too big, it might cause computational difficulties (Camm et al. 1990) because of numerical instabilities and large gaps in the continuous relaxation, making the branch and bound too slow. A compromise solution is obtained by considering $M_1 = M_2 = 100$ in our problems. Setting M_1

and M_2 equal to 100, not a huge number, may indeed exclude the optimal solution of the original problem. This is not a big issue, since the original problem is nothing but a surrogate of our real aim, namely, classifying correctly forthcoming individuals. On the other hand, this constraint may also be seen as a regularization constraint, since it forces the variables involved to take relatively small values, as already happens with the variables λ_i , already forced to be below $C/2$. In other words, though at the expense of excluding the optimal solution of the proxy optimization problem, setting a not too large value for M_1 and M_2 can be seen as an extra regularization, thus preventing overfit.

Note that an alternative formulation, avoiding big M constraints is obtained by using the Specially Ordered Sets of Type 1 (SOS1) (Bertsimas and Weismantel (2005), see also Silva (2017) and Bertsimas et al. (2016) for some examples of SOS1). However, we prefer to maintain the big M_1 and M_2 for two reasons. On the one hand, the use of SOS1 would involve quadratic constraints, which would make the problem even more difficult to solve. For example, constraint $0 \leq \mu_t \leq M_2 z_t$ would become $(\mu_t, 1 - z_t)$:SOS1 and $0 \leq \mu_t$. This is equivalent to $\mu_t(1 - z_t) = 0$ and $0 \leq \mu_t$, which includes, as we can see, a non-convex quadratic constraint. On the other hand, not every solver has implemented the SOS1 method or is capable to solve quadratic mixed integer problems with non-convex quadratic constraints. In addition, even if it can manage SOS1-type constraints, it might perform the conversion to the problem with a big M automatically, and thus we would be again with big M constraints, now controlled by the solver and not by ourselves.

3.3 Performance estimation

The estimation of the performance of the novel CSVM is based on a K -fold cross validation (CV) as follows, see Kohavi et al. (1995). Generally, $K=10$, but for those datasets with more than 1000 samples, $K = 5$ so that the running times are lower. Note that, apart from tuning γ , the regularization parameters C_+ and C_- introduced in Section 1 also need to be tuned. In order to make the CSVM procedure quicker, our experiments are based on choosing $C_+ = C/|I_+|$ and $C_- = C/|I_-|$, so only one parameter C shall be tuned for the CSVM, but not for the SVM(C_+, C_-), in which both C_+ and C_- are tuned independently. As it will be seen later, this is not a crucial issue. Hence, for a given pair of parameters (C, γ) , the process consists mainly on solving a standard SVM using all the instances $(I \cup J)$, and collect the values of λ (from the dual formulation of the SVM) as well as the value of β . Once the SVM is solved, and with the purpose of providing an initial solution for the CSVM, the value of β is slightly changed (maintaining the values of λ 's fixed) until the desired number of instances well classified is reached. Then, the values of β and λ 's obtained are set as initial solutions for CSVM. In addition, depending on whether each instance in J is well classified or not, we set their values of z as 0 or 1 as initial values for the CSVM.

We should make the selection of the best pair (C, γ) in each of the previous folds. In order to do that, a 10-fold CV (5-fold CV for datasets with more of 1000 samples, in order to reduce the running times) as before is made for each pair in a grid given by the 121 different combinations of $C = 2^{(-5:5)}$ and $\gamma = 2^{(-5:5)}$ ($C_+ = 2^{(-5:5)}$, $C_- = 2^{(-5:5)}$ and $\gamma = 2^{(-5:5)}$ for $\text{SVM}(C_+, C_-)$). The general criterion used to select the best pair of parameters is the accuracy. However, in cases where the datasets are severely unbalanced in the classes size (when one of the classes has a weight less than a 30% of the total size), the G-mean (Tang et al. 2009), which is defined as $\sqrt{\text{TPR} \times \text{TNR}}$, is used to perform the parameter tuning instead. Finally, the average values of TPR and TNR obtained in the first CV, in addition to their standard deviations, are calculated.

For a better understanding, the previous algorithm is summarized in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1: Pseudocode for CSVM

```

1 Split data ( $D$ ) into “folds” subsets,  $D = \{D_1, \dots, D_{folds}\}$ .
2 for  $kf = 1, \dots, folds$  do
3   Set  $Validation = D_{kf}$  and  $I \cup J = D - \{D_{kf}\}$ .
4   for each pair  $(C, \gamma)$  in grid  $(\{2^{(-5:5)}\}, \{2^{(-5:5)}\})$  do
5     Split  $D - \{D_{kf}\} = D^*$  into “folds2” subsets,  $D^* = \{D_1^*, \dots, D_{folds2}^*\}$ .
6     for  $kf2 = 1, \dots, folds2$  do
7       Set  $Validation^* = D_{kf2}^*$  and  $I^* \cup J^* = D^* - \{D_{kf2}^*\}$ .
8       Run standard SVM over  $I^* \cup J^*$ .
9       Move  $\beta$  of SVM until the instances are correctly classified.
10      Run problem CSVM over  $I^*, J^*$  with initial solutions from before.
11      Validate over  $Validation^*$ , getting the accuracy ( $ACC[kf2]$ ).
12    end
13    Calculate the average accuracy  $(\sum_{kf2} ACC[kf2])/folds2 = \overline{ACC}$ .
14    if  $\overline{ACC} \geq bestACC$  then
15      Set  $bestACC = \overline{ACC}$ ,  $best\gamma = \gamma$  and  $bestC = C$ .
16    end
17  end
18  Run standard SVM over  $I \cup J$  with the parameters  $best\gamma$  and  $bestC$ .
19  Move  $\beta$  of SVM until the instances are correctly classified.
20  Run problem CSVM over  $I, J$  with initial solutions from the previous step.
21  Validate over  $Validation$ , getting the correct classification probabilities
    ( $\text{TPR}[kf], \text{TNR}[kf]$ ).
22 end
23 Calculate the average values for  $\text{TPR}$  and  $\text{TNR}$ .
```

Finally, we want to clarify that for our experiments we have selected I as the first half of $I \cup J$ and J as the second one.

3.4 Data description

The performance, in terms of correct classification probabilities and accuracy, is illustrated using 6 real-life datasets from the UCI and Keel repositories (Lichman 2013 and Alcalá-Fdez et al. 2009). In particular, the datasets are **australian** (Statlog (Australian Credit Approval) Data Set), **votes** (Congressional Voting Records Data Set), **wisconsin** (Breast Cancer Wisconsin (Diagnostic) Data Set), **german** (Statlog (German Credit Data) Data Set), **pageBlocks** (Page Blocks Classification (Imbalanced: 0) data set) and **biodeg** (QSAR biodegradation Data Set).

Details concerning the distribution of the classes in the considered datasets are provided by Table 2. The first two columns give the name and number of

Name	V	$ \Omega $	$ \Omega_+ $ (%)
australian	14	690	307 (44.5%)
votes	16	435	267 (61.4 %)
wisconsin	30	569	212 (37.3 %)
german	45	1000	300 (30%)
pageBlocks	10	5472	558 (10.2%)
biodeg	41	1055	356 (33.7%)

Table 2 Details concerning the implementation of the CSVM for the considered datasets.

attributes for each set. The values $|\Omega|$ and $|\Omega_+|$ represent, respectively, the size for each dataset and the number of positive instances in Ω . Finally, the percentage of positive instances is compiled in the last column.

Note that prior to running the different experiments, data have been standardized, that is to say, each attribute has zero mean and unit variance.

As a remark, we want to express that for the two biggest datasets (those that have more than 1000 samples), an alternative is proposed in order to reduce the computational times. First, to train the classifier, instead of using the training samples, we have built clusters of training points of the same class via the k-means method. The number of clusters was selected so that the proportion of original positive and negative instances was maintained. Also, we took into consideration the number of instances per cluster to train the SVM. In the validation sample, we kept the instances as they were originally.

3.5 Results

In this section we illustrate the performance of the CSVM in comparison with the classic SVM, the $SVM(C_+, C_-)$ and the *Sliding β strategy*. As previously commented, the purpose will be to increase the TPR. Note that, even though from Section 2.3 the CSVM problem is always feasible using the training sample, it may happen that the desired performance is not achieved in the validation sample.

Table 3 reports the average rates (and under them, and in parenthesis,

Name		SVM	SVM(C_+, C_-)	Sliding β	CSVM
		Mean (Std)	Mean (Std)	Mean (Target) (Std)	Mean (Target) (Std)
australian	TPR	0.83 (0.071)	0.806 (0.093)	0.821 (0.855) (0.073)	0.903 (0.855) (0.05)
	TNR	0.863 (0.079)	0.878 (0.088)	0.855 (0.068)	0.772 (0.081)
votes	TPR	0.963 (0.04)	0.945 (0.042)	0.971 (0.988) (0.037)	0.978 (0.988) (0.026)
	TNR	0.951 (0.031)	0.941 (0.037)	0.91 (0.063)	0.922 (0.04)
wisconsin	TPR	0.948 (0.049)	0.962 (0.027)	0.989 (0.973) (0.017)	0.965 (0.973) (0.037)
	TNR	0.99 (0.017)	0.931 (0.07)	0.953 (0.045)	0.945 (0.045)
german	TPR	0.464 (0.103)	0.89 (0.08)	0.043 (0.65) (0.023)	0.671 (0.65) (0.164)
	TNR	0.847 (0.031)	0.407 (0.069)	0.996 (0.009)	0.668 (0.111)
pageBlocks	TPR	0.807 (0.03)	0.557 (0.361)	0.819 (0.832) (0.981)	0.859 (0.832) (0.045)
	TNR	0.988 (0.004)	0.901 (0.088)	0.981 (0.006)	0.965 (0.012)
biodeg	TPR	0.783 (0.084)	0.793 (0.083)	0.797 (0.808) (0.095)	0.852 (0.808) (0.057)
	TNR	0.909 (0.032)	0.839 (0.037)	0.891 (0.037)	0.833 (0.05)

Table 3 Results under the SVM, SVM(C_+, C_-), the *Sliding β strategy* and the novel CSVM. Target rate: TPR

their standard deviations) obtained under the SVM, SVM(C_+, C_-), *Sliding β strategy* and CSVM, for the experiment described in Section 3.1, that is, when $\widehat{\text{TPR}} \geq \min \left\{ 1, \text{TPR}_0 + \sqrt{\frac{\log 0.05}{-2n}} + 0.025 \right\}$ is imposed. Also, the target values (in parenthesis in the third and forth columns) to be achieved for the TPR are shown.

Some comments arise from the table. In the case of **australian**, we trivially considered “+” as the positive class and “-” as the negative. The SVM(C_+, C_-) slightly improves the TNR when it is compared with the standard SVM, but yields a worse value in the TPR, which is the rate to be improved. When the *Sliding β strategy* is used, although a target value of 0.855 is imposed, even a lower value that the one got with the SVM is obtained, with a lower TNR value also. On the other hand, when the CSVM is used instead, the increase is not only of 0.025 points but of 0.073, obviously at the expense of the other class. Hence, the best TPR is obtained for the CSVM.

We shall analyze next the results for **votes**, which has two classes: “democrat” and “republican”. Since in principle there is no interest in a better classifica-

tion of one of the classes, the majority class (“democrat”) will be identified as the positive class. From the table it can be seen how the results under the $SVM(C_+, C_-)$ are poorer than under the classic SVM. If the *Sliding β strategy* is used instead, an increase in the TPR is obtained but the rate does not achieve the target value. Even though the CSVM does not achieve the target value in the validation set, here again, this novel approach achieves the best TPR.

Concerning **wisconsin** dataset, it has two classes: “malignant” and “benign”. Here, we consider as positive the “malignant” class, which is clearly the class of interest. The results for the $SVM(C_+, C_-)$ are better than those obtained under the SVM, but it does not achieve the target value. When the *Sliding β strategy* is used, the target value for the TPR is achieved, while reducing the value for the TNR with respect to the SVM. Then, when we use the CSVM, the TPR is a bit higher than when the $SVM(C_+, C_-)$ is used, but lower than the one obtained for the *Sliding β strategy*. The same happens for the TNR. In this case, the method that performs the best is the *Sliding β strategy*.

Next, we shall analyze **german** dataset, which is composed by two classes: good and bad credit risk. The class of interest and hence the positive one, is “bad credit risk”. Here, the $SVM(C_+, C_-)$ improves in a significant way the estimation of the TPR in comparison to the classic SVM; however, this is achieved at the expense of worsening the TNR. The *Sliding β strategy* performs very poorly in the case of the TPR but provides in contrast a very high TNR. The CSVM gets the most balanced result: the TPR exceeds the target values, and at the same time, the TNR is not notably affected.

We next describe the results obtained for the **pageBlocks** dataset which, as it has been previously commented, is a strongly unbalanced dataset with a dimension higher than in the previous cases. The two classes for this dataset are “text” and “graphic” areas. In addition, the “graphic” areas instances are less frequent (10.2 %). Assume that for this problem the interest is in distinguishing the “graphic” areas from the “text” areas, therefore, the class to be controlled will be the “graphic” one. The results show how the $SVM(C_+, C_-)$ obtains the opposite effect than the pursued. Both the TPR and TNR are lower than when the classic SVM is used. In the case of using the *Sliding β strategy*, the TPR is increased but it does not reach the imposed target. On the other hand, the TNR is slightly reduced. For the CSVM, the target value in the TPR is reached, resulting in a small decrease in the TNR.

Finally, we present the results for **biodeg**, with two classes: “ready biodegradable” and “not ready biodegradable”. Originally, Mansouri et al. (2013), classification models were used to discriminate “ready biodegradable” from “not ready biodegradable”, being “ready biodegradable” considered as the positive class. Here again, $SVM(C_+, C_-)$ improves the TPR with respect to the classic SVM. The *Sliding β strategy* outperforms the $SVM(C_+, C_-)$ but only the CSVM obtains an estimated TPR larger than the imposed lower bound. Note that, in contrast, the TNR under the CSVM is slightly lower than the values under the benchmark approaches.

Overall, the target value is almost always achieved when the CSVM is used. In the cases this does not occur, we obtain a close value. However, although initially one may think that good results will be obtained for the *Sliding β strategy*, such naive procedure does not achieve the target value so frequently. The same occurs with the SVM(C_+ , C_-). Hence, we can conclude that the method that provides more control on the performance measures is the CSVM, which highlights the novelty of our proposal.

4 Conclusions

In this paper, we propose a new supervised learning SVM-based method, the CSVM, with the purpose of controlling a specific performance measure. Such classifier is built via a reformulation of the classic SVM, where novel constraints including integer variables are added. The final optimization problem is a MIQP problem, which can be solved using standard solvers as Gurobi or CPLEX. In order to guarantee that the performance rate is lower bounded by a fixed constant with a high confidence, some theoretical foundations are provided. The applicability of this cost-sensitive SVM has been demonstrated by numerical experiments on benchmark data sets.

We conclude that it is possible to control the classification rates in one class, possibly, but not necessarily, at the expense of the performance on the other class. This highly contrasts with the naive approach in which, once the SVM is solved, its intercept is moved to enhance the positive rates in one class, necessarily deteriorating the performance in the other class. The results presented confirm the power of our approach.

Although, for simplicity, all numerical results are presented just adding one performance constraint, one constraint per class, as well as an overall accuracy, may be added in our approach. Also for simplicity, we addressed here two-ways data matrices and two-class problems; however, this approach could be extended to the case when using more complex data as multi-class or *multi-way* arrays (Lyu et al. 2017), which are very common in biomedical research. On the other hand, an alternative perspective for addressing the SVM regularization is to consider different norms (Yao and Lee 2014).

Finally, another possible extension is to perform a feature selection which uses the proposed constraints in order to control the misclassification costs, see Benítez-Peña et al. (2018). Such a process is an essential step in tasks such as high-dimensional microarray classification problems (Guo 2010).

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The KKT conditions are, therefore

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \omega} = 0 &\Rightarrow \omega = \sum_{s \in I} (\lambda_s/2) y_s x_s + \sum_{t \in J(z)} (\mu_t/2) y_t x_t \\
\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \beta} = 0 &\Rightarrow 0 = \sum_{s \in I} \lambda_s y_s + \sum_{t \in J(z)} \mu_t y_t \\
\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \xi_i} = 0 &\Rightarrow 0 = -\lambda_i - \delta_i + C_+ && i \in I : y_i = +1 \\
\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \xi_i} = 0 &\Rightarrow 0 = -\lambda_i - \delta_i + C_- && i \in I : y_i = -1 \\
0 &\leq \lambda_i && i \in I \\
0 &\leq \mu_t && t \in J(z) \\
0 &\leq \delta_i && i \in I
\end{aligned}$$

Note that we can replace, without loss of generality, $\lambda_s/2$, $\mu_t/2$ by λ_s and μ_t , respectively. Then, in the condition $\partial \mathcal{L}/\partial \beta = 0$ we have

$$0 = \sum_{s \in I} 2\lambda_s y_s + \sum_{t \in J(z)} 2\mu_t y_t,$$

that can be simplified to

$$0 = \sum_{s \in I} \lambda_s y_s + \sum_{t \in J(z)} \mu_t y_t,$$

as stated. In addition, the condition $\partial \mathcal{L}/\partial \xi_i = 0$ is transformed into

$$0 = -2\lambda_i - \delta_i + C_+, \quad i \in I : y_i = +1$$

and

$$0 = -2\lambda_i - \delta_i + C_-, \quad i \in I : y_i = -1.$$

Furthermore, since these results must be equivalent to the case if we had maintained the previously removed constraint, we have $\mu_t = 0$ when $z_t = 0$, $t \in J$ and $\mu_t \geq 0$ when $z_t = 1$, $t \in J$. This can be summarized as $0 \leq \mu_t \leq M_2 z_t$, $t \in J$. Also, as usual, δ_i is removed since we add

$$0 \leq \lambda_i \leq C_+/2, \quad i \in I : y_i = +1$$

and

$$0 \leq \lambda_i \leq C_-/2, \quad i \in I : y_i = -1,$$

as we know that $\delta_i \geq 0$. Therefore, the KKT conditions result:

$$\begin{aligned}
\omega &= \sum_{s \in I} \lambda_s y_s x_s + \sum_{t \in J} \mu_t y_t x_t \\
0 &= \sum_{s \in I} \lambda_s y_s + \sum_{t \in J} \mu_t y_t \\
0 &\leq \lambda_s \leq C_+/2 && s \in I : y_i = +1 \\
0 &\leq \lambda_s \leq C_-/2 && s \in I : y_i = -1 \\
0 &\leq \mu_t \leq M_2 z_t && t \in J.
\end{aligned}$$

Note that we have replaced all the $J(z)$ by J using the previous clarification.

Thus, substituting the previous expressions into the second optimization problem, the partial dual of such problem can be calculated, yielding

$$\begin{aligned}
\min_z \quad & \min_{\lambda, \mu, \beta, \xi} \left(\sum_{s \in I} \lambda_s y_s x_s + \sum_{t \in J} \mu_t y_t x_t \right)^\top \left(\sum_{s \in I} \lambda_s y_s x_s + \sum_{t \in J} \mu_t y_t x_t \right) + \\
& + C_+ \sum_{i \in I: y_i = +1} \xi_i + C_- \sum_{i \in I: y_i = -1} \xi_i \\
\text{s.t. } z_j \in \{0, 1\} \quad j \in J \quad & \text{s.t. } y_i \left(\left(\sum_{s \in I} \lambda_s y_s x_s + \sum_{t \in J} \mu_t y_t x_t \right)^\top x_i + \beta \right) \geq 1 - \xi_i \quad i \in I \\
\hat{p}_\ell \geq p_{0\ell}^* \quad \ell \in L \quad & y_j \left(\left(\sum_{s \in I} \lambda_s y_s x_s + \sum_{t \in J} \mu_t y_t x_t \right)^\top x_j + \beta \right) \geq 1 - M_1(1 - z_j) \quad j \in J \\
& \xi_i \geq 0 \quad i \in I \\
& \sum_{i \in I} \lambda_i y_i + \sum_{j \in J} \mu_j y_j = 0 \\
& 0 \leq \lambda_i \leq C_+/2 \quad i \in I: y_i = +1 \\
& 0 \leq \lambda_i \leq C_-/2 \quad i \in I: y_i = -1 \\
& 0 \leq \mu_j \leq M_2 z_j \quad j \in J.
\end{aligned}$$

Finally, since this problem only depends on the observation via the inner product, we can use the kernel trick and Problem (CSVM) is obtained.

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